

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING IN EDUCATION AND MODERN APPROACHES

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Currently, an active search and implementation of new forms and methods of teaching students is underway. In this regard, the main tasks that a modern teacher should set for himself are the following: conducting training in an interactive mode; increasing students' interest in the discipline being studied; bringing the educational process closer to the practice of everyday life, namely: the formation of communication skills, adaptation to rapidly changing living conditions, socialization, increasing psychological stress resistance, teaching conflict resolution skills, etc. Thus, the main task of a qualitatively new educational system is to achieve a sustainable interest of students in the subject being studied, to self-education from the very first years of study, as well as to attract them to scientific research. To do this, it is necessary to initially set up the system of psychological thinking of students to be able to gain knowledge and master the future profession. The student, as a future specialist, must understand how, having acquired social and professional skills, he can apply them in practice. It is innovative methods and technologies in teaching that can help the teacher in solving the tasks. Initially, teaching should include two main components: sending and receiving information. The main problem of many teachers is that they try to spread knowledge through the prism of their understanding of the subject, focusing only on their own experience and beliefs. When controlling individual knowledge, the student tries to reproduce the received material as accurately as possible, while ignoring his own judgments and reflections, since, in his opinion, they may not correspond to the content of the subject or distort the received material. In this situation, both parties lose: a teacher who does not develop his subject according to the needs of students, and a student who receives purely standardized material, often unsuitable for use in a real, dynamically developing economic life. Innovative methods in teaching include the assessment of creative approaches to understanding the discipline, as well as the ability to find non-standard solutions to standard problems. This is especially

important and related to reforming higher education. Today, a number of trends stand out, which are associated, firstly, with a multi-level system of training specialists, secondly, with the powerful enrichment of universities with modern information technologies, and, thirdly, with the inclusion of Russian universities in the update, taking into account the requirements of world standards. Today, the teacher's value criterion is changing: he is valued not because he knows a lot, but because he effectively knows how to organize the process of self-development of the student and himself, which is especially important in modern conditions. Education should become an interesting and exciting process that contributes to the personal and professional growth of a person, and not a formal procedure for obtaining a certificate. From these positions, the following interactive forms of learning can be distinguished that contribute to the solution of the identified tasks:

- ♣ trainings;
- ♣ brainstorming method;
- ♣ synectics;
- ♣ Delphi method.

Taking into account modern approaches to the organization of the educational process in universities, much attention should be paid to the self-education of a future specialist who wants to deepen his knowledge in his specialty. This is facilitated by the conduct of trainings, which are the material for independent work of the student. Trainings not only allow to form the ideological component of the subject, but also instill skills in working with the subject. Today it is one of the most convenient forms for teachers and students. Trainings can be expanded, deepened, creatively refined and discussed both at seminars and with the help of Internet technologies, Internet conferences, round tables. The methodological possibilities of trainings are much wider than it is commonly believed. They allow you to pay attention to each question asked, stimulate additional reference to the literature and sources, play an important role in awakening the attraction of scientific understanding to the subject. All these qualities are not fully disclosed by modern education. One of the advantages of the training is that it is a tool for the active involvement of all students in the learning process. Training is a special method of gaining knowledge, which is different in that its participants learn from their own experience, where everyone can see and realize their pluses and minuses. The next interactive approach that contributes to the creative

development of the individual and stimulates the activity of students in the classroom is the brainstorming method. The brainstorming method is the development of a solution through the free generation of ideas by the participants in the procedure. This method is designed to generate solutions at an innovative level. He makes clear demands on the conditions of the procedure and the analytical abilities of the members of the idea processing group. The brainstorming method, also called the brainstorming method, was proposed in 1953 by the American inventor and entrepreneur A. Osborne [1]. Its purpose was to develop recommendations for organizing a procedure for the collective search for ideas and putting forward proposals in such areas as science, technology, trade and management. At present, this method is well known and widely used. Properly planned and conducted brainstorming allows you to achieve results that are impossible using other methods. The brainstorming method involves a creative approach to solving problems and problems. The advantage of the method in teaching is that with its help the teacher can involve students who are usually not active in the classroom and do not express their opinions publicly. When conducting a lesson using the brainstorming method, such opinions will not only be heard, but will also be useful in generating ideas, since the main difference between the method and other solution search procedures is the formation of the widest possible range of ideas and ways to solve the problem. The basis of the methodology of the method is to go beyond the boundaries of the traditional ideas that the group has in the area under consideration, and put forward the most extraordinary proposals. The more alternative ideas are expressed, the more original will be the solution of the task. The absence of criticism as the main condition of the method allows the participants of the brainstorming group not to be afraid that the teacher or a more authoritative member of the group will negatively perceive the idea. Brainstorming allows students to express themselves, unleash their creativity and present ideas that would not otherwise be voiced. Brainstorming is carried out in two stages. The first stage is the collective generation of ideas. At this stage, conditions are created for putting forward as many diverse ideas and proposals as possible. The duration of one session of collective generation of ideas is no more than 20-30 minutes. All ideas expressed are recorded in the minutes. The basic rule of brainstorming is a strict ban on any criticism of the proposals made. All proposals, without exception, should be taken into

consideration and recorded, no matter how fantastic and even absurd they may seem. No preliminary assessment of the judgments expressed is allowed, and it is forbidden to express one's attitude even with facial expressions and gestures. Only in this way can an environment be created that is most conducive to the free creative search for solutions to the problem. Moreover, the expression of extraordinary and, in a sense, fantastic ideas should not only be allowed, but also welcomed. The second stage is the analysis of the ideas put forward. During this stage, these proposals are analyzed and summarized, conclusions are drawn and the final version of the solution is formulated. For this, two groups are created: a group of idea generators and a group of expert analysts. A further improvement of the brainstorming method is the synectics method. This method was proposed by W.J. Gordon, who formulated it as a problem-solving method when he led the Invention Research Group [3]. Synectics - translated from English "synectics" - "combination of heterogeneous elements." As with brainstorming, when using synectics, groups are formed, but with the only difference that these groups are permanent. Also, in the synectic model of assault, criticism is acceptable, but only that which allows you to improve or develop the ideas expressed. As a result, the student gets used to constant criticism and is not afraid of it; perceives criticism adequately as an improving tool. The technology of synectic storming is similar to the technology of brainstorming with the active use of analogies. In practice, five types of analogies are used, called synectics operators.

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